

Adsorptive and Photoelectrochemical Properties of Flavins onto Zinc Oxide Interfaces

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The adsorption behaviour of flavin mononucleotide (FMN) and riboflavin (RF) on zinc oxide (ZnO) powder is characterised as isotherm type-I, and interfacial parameters are deduced according to the Langmuir theory. Cyclic voltammetry of FMN and RF on zinc electrodes at different adsorption potentials and illumination conditions, evidences photo-induced electron transfer into oxide-zinc electrodes related to electronic coupling, surface mediation and adsorption properties of the flavins under investigation.

Elucidation of electron transfer pathways for sensitive and stereospecific biomolecules, clears the way for the construction of a variety of biosensors. The molecules, flavin mononucleotide (FMN) and riboflavin (RF) form thermodynamically reversible redox systems, fulfilling the criteria of a quinoid reductive or oxidative system^{1,2}, with the ability to operate in either mode, unique among biomolecules^{3,4}.

Flavins are very sensitive to light. On absorption of light, hydrogen is transferred from the hydroxylic side-chain to the isoalloxazine ring³. The irreversibility of the process can be suppressed by addition of an external electron-donor. It was thought⁵ that photoinitiated reactions of adsorbates on metal surfaces would be inefficient due to the quenching of electronic excited states by metal. However, formation of a Langmuir-Blodgett monolayer of flavins onto oxide surfaces has been reported^{9,11} to enhance the two overlapping 1 electron transfer, so that charge transfer may be faster (picosecond scale) than electronic quenching⁷. Adsorption processes of flavins onto metal oxide surfaces can present electrostatic and nonelectrostatic (specific) interactions^{3,4}. Only tentative conclusions about the adsorption mechanisms were obtained due to lack of experimental and modelling data which are scanty in the literature.

The present communication presents the following topics. (i) Determination of the composition of interfacial films of flavins (FMN and RF) onto zinc oxide (ZnO) par-

ticles of well defined size. The composition of the interfacial films at fixed pH has been determined and basic parameters deduced, such as surface density, area per molecule and equilibrium adsorption constants. The model assumes that the points of maximum surface density are corresponding to the complete oxide surface coverage, with monolayer formation, characterising Langmuir isotherm¹². (ii) Cyclic voltammetry of flavins (FMN and RF) on zinc electrodes by varying experimental conditions, such as, adsorption potential and the influence of light as shown in Scheme 1^{17-10,13,14}.

Scheme 1

The importance of interlocking groups, as phosphates (inexistent for RF), is interpreted as being an additional connection, enhancing adsorption properties, promoting electronic coupling between FMN and the oxide-zinc electrode and acting as surface mediators for the molecules in solution.

Results and Discussion

Flavins present high photoelectrochemical stability and hence can be used in surface-modified photogalvanic cells⁵⁻⁷. Reactions of flavins with Hg, Pt and Ti were investigated^{1,4,9}, and immobilisation on electrodes by chemi-

cal modification^{2,11} has proven to be effective. Earlier work¹², characterised as physicochemisorption of FMN and RF onto oxides TiO₂ (P-25), ZrO₂ (VP) and Al₂O₃ (C) (Degussa), showed Langmuir behaviour. In the present work, isotherms of flavin mononucleotide (FMN) and riboflavin (RF) onto ZnO (particle diameter ≈ 5 nm) at a solid-liquid interface, have been derived. A plot of equilibrium concentration (C_{eq}) vs surface density (Γ) (Fig. 1) shows

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherms of FMN and RF on ZnO particles; Γ is the surface density and C_{eq} the solution concentration after adsorption equilibrium is attained.

isotherms type-I, with an horizontal *plateau*, suggesting chemisorption¹⁵ on the microporous solid, and plots of $1/C_{eq}$ vs $1/\Gamma$ show linearity for both FMN and RF, characterising Langmuir isotherms. The model assumes that the amount which can be accommodated in a completely filled single molecular layer on the oxide surface, corresponds to the formation of molecular monolayers. Basic parameters, Γ (surface density), APM (area per molecule) and K (adsorption equilibrium constant, $K = K_a/K_d$; K_a = adsorption rate constant, K_d = desorption rate constant) have been calculated (Table 1) by considering this model. The distinct adsorptive behaviour of the flavins, by considering K values can be related to the additional connection, a phosphate group (inexistent for RF), which enhances adsorption properties of FMN⁹.

TABLE 1—MAXIMUM SURFACE DENSITIES (Γ^{max}), AREA PER MOLECULE (APM) AND ADSORPTION CONSTANTS (K) OF FMN AND RF ON ZnO PARTICLES

Adsorbates	$10^{-7} \Gamma^{max}$ mol cm ⁻²	APM Å ²	$10^3 K$ M ⁻¹
FMN	5.0	0.04	2.3
RF	1.0	0.12	1.2

The adsorption equilibrium constant, K can be related to Γ^{max} (surface density at maximum surface coverage), C_{eq} by the equation,

$$1/\Gamma = 1/K \cdot \Gamma^{max} C_{eq} + 1/\Gamma^{max} \quad (1)$$

The weaker adsorption behaviour of riboflavin in comparison to FMN is reflected by lower K values onto ZnO, in agreement with the earlier reports¹¹; the linkage between RF and a glassy carbon electrode is suggested to be established only through the hydroxyl group of the riboflavin. Shinohara *et al.*⁹ considered the redox-active isoalloxazine moiety as not being directly adsorbed on the surface of the semiconductor. Earlier work⁴ suggests that flavins form a monomolecular layer with their planes parallel to the electrode surface, but the adsorption not being a 'simple' process. By considering the present data (Fig. 1 and Table 1), adsorption processes of flavins onto ZnO powder present maximum surface densities (Γ^{max}) for FMN (5.10^{-7} mol cm⁻²) and RF (1.10^{-7} mol cm⁻²). Even with some regard to experimental error, it reflects more than monolayer coverage ($\approx 5 \times 10^{-10}$ mol cm⁻²)¹⁶. The observed surface coverage corresponds to several hundreds of monolayers, as described before¹¹. It evidences strong attachment of FMN

Fig. 2(A). Cyclic voltammogram of a 1.03 cm² zinc electrode; illumination with monochromatic light at 450 nm, scan rate 2 mV s⁻¹, and adsorption potential 1.0 V of [RF]: (-----) zero and (—) $1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M.

molecules via phosphate group (connecting point), suggesting a closely packed conformation with possible stacked spatial arrangement.

Zinc electrode reaction of adsorbed flavins: Cyclic voltammograms (CV) of FMN and RF were recorded in 0.1 M Li₂SO₄, 0.1 M hydroquinone (HQ) as the redox couple (Scheme 1) solutions at pH 5.0, measured on a Pt flag. The CV determined in the potential range initial: $E_i = -1.20$ V and final: $E_f = -0.90$ V, did not account the standard redox potential domain of the flavins ($E^\circ = -0.46$

V vs SCE) under investigation. The present work investigated flavin electron transfer reactions at more negative potentials. CV shown by dashed line in Fig. 2(A) indicates that the background current does not make an important contribution in the selected potential region; the presence of RF (full line) demonstrates RF adsorption on Zn electrode, once CV is shifted.

Fig. 2(B). Cyclic voltammogram of a 1.43 cm² zinc electrode; scan rate : 2 mV s⁻¹, adsorption potential 1.0 V and [FMN] = 2.8 × 10⁻⁵ M : (-----) dark and (—) monochromatic light at 450 nm.

By considering that the maximum adsorption band of FMN and RF is located at 448 nm, the cathodic peak current density (J_p) (determined at -0.95 V) (Fig. 2(A) and (B)) was monitored by considering the following variables : FMN concentration (zero, 0.028 mM and 0.1 mM), RF con-

Fig. 3. Cathodic peak current density vs scan rate for zinc electrodes respectively 1.491 and 1.03 cm², in FMN (1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M) and RF (5.5 × 10⁻⁴ M) solutions, scan rate varied and adsorption potential = 1.0 V, adsorption time = 60 s and illumination by monochromatic light at 450 nm.

centration (zero and 0.55 mM), illumination conditions (dark, white light and monochromatic light at 450 nm),

Fig. 4(A). Diagram illustrating the applied potential effect, by relating cathodic peak current density vs illumination conditions at different adsorption potentials (-1.20 and -1.0 V), for zinc electrodes in FMN (1.10⁻⁴ M) solutions.

Fig. 4(B). Diagram illustrating the concentration effect of RF, by relating cathodic peak current density vs illumination conditions at different RF concentrations (zero, 0.55 mM) for zinc electrodes.

adsorption potential ($E_{ads} = -1.20$ V and $E_{ads} = -1.0$ V). The presence of flavins and light (white and monochromatic) increased J_p in all studied systems, evidencing electron transfer^{13,14}. The monochromatic light effect ($\lambda = 450$ nm) proved to be more effective at adsorption potentials, $E_{ads} = -1.0$ V (oxide formation domain) for FMN systems (Fig. 4(A) and 4(B)). The increase of J_p and C_p (Fig. 3, Table 2) for illuminated systems confirms heterogeneous electron transfer from excited dye to the oxide-zinc interface. The existence of different rates for FMN and RF suggests different adsorptive behaviour and/or distinct injection sites⁸.

In the concentration range studied (Table 2), there is a linear relationship between peak current or peak current

TABLE 2-V VALUES FOR CATHODIC PEAK CURRENT DENSITY (J_p), APPARENT SURFACE DENSITY (Γ^{app}), CHARGE DENSITY (C_p), ROUGHNESS FACTOR (ρ) AND PEAK POTENTIAL (E_p) FOR FMN (1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M) AND RF (5.5 × 10⁻⁴ M) SOLUTION/ZINC OXIDE ELECTRODES

Scan rate = 2 mV s ⁻¹ , adsorption potential = -1.0 V	Adorbate	Illumination	J_p mA cm ⁻²	C_p mC cm ⁻²	10 ⁻⁸ Γ^{app} mol cm ⁻²	ρ	E_p mV
	RF	Dark	0.23	5.9	3.06	2.8	-1143
	RF	$\lambda = 450$ nm	0.25	6.4	3.32	3.0	-1141
	FMN	Dark	0.75	19.3	9.98	3.8	-1144
	FMN	$\lambda = 450$ nm	0.88	22.6	11.7	4.5	-1148

density and scan rate. At scan rates below 8 mV s^{-1} , a straight-line passing through the origin is obtained for both adsorbates, FMN and RF (Fig. 3). Higher scan rates reveal no more linearity, probably due to kinetic effects. The slope difference for FNM (Illum. and dark) is higher if compared to RF, in agreement with the higher Γ^{max} value for the former. The electrochemical process can be described by an equation with the sweep rate dependence equation (2),

$$\Gamma^{\text{app}} = i_p \cdot 4 \cdot R \cdot T / n^2 \cdot F^2 \cdot A \cdot v \quad (2)$$

Γ^{app} can be determined by using equation (2) (Table 2). Charge density (C_p) can be calculated by using equation (3),

$$C_p = nF\Gamma \quad (3)$$

The values so obtained are significant only for low scan rates, as those selected from Table 2 (2 mV s^{-1}).

Fig. 4(A) presents the effect of the applied potential (-1.20 and -1.0 V) for FMN (0.1 mM) by varying illumination conditions : dark, white light and monochromatic light at 450 nm . The most expressive peak current density (J_p) and charge density (C_p) was observed for -1.0 V (adsorption potential) and illumination at 450 nm . In counterpart, for RF systems, J_p and C_p presented its maximum value for adsorption potential -1.0 V and white light (Fig. 4(B)). For an adsorbed molecule on a metal surface where the metal substrate and adsorbate wave function overlap, an excitation to an electronic level above the Fermi level can lead to electron tunneling to the metal by resonant charge transfer⁵. The electronic orbital overlap between FMN and the metal is formed when FMN is adsorbed on the oxide-electrode. Likely coordination groups come from the lone-pairs electrons of nitrogen and oxygen on ring-III⁷ producing a change in molecular geometry with electron density rearrangement on the isoalloxazine rings in order to minimise the system's total energy to form a new electronic orbital overlap between FMN and the electrode surface. In the case of RF, the linkage through the hydroxyl group of the sugar unit, leaves the redox characteristics of RF unaltered, as it does not affect the electron density of the ring¹¹. The attachment of riboflavin is proposed to be at the hydroxyl group and this idea is in conformity with the earlier literature²⁸.

Fig. 5 represents the concentration effect for FMN (3.10^{-5} M) and RF (6.10^{-4} M) as starting solution at selected conditions : adsorption potential -1.0 V and monochromatic light at 450 nm . The adsorptive properties for FMN onto zinc oxide are approximately 5 times higher than for RF (Fig. 1, Table 1). The starting solution value for RF is 20 times higher and should compensate the distinct adsorptive behaviour, if excited dye molecules from solution were involved. It may not be the case for RF sys-

Fig. 5. Diagram illustrating the concentration effect (phosphate group), by relating cathodic peak current density vs flavin concentration (systems with adsorption potential at -1.0 V and monochromatic light at 450 nm); [FMN] = $3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ and [RF] = $6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$.

tems. According to the Schottky mode¹⁹, the degree of bending of the bands necessary for the band energy at the surface to overlap the electronic states in solution affects the electron transfer probability, once it determines the degree of electron availability. The adsorbate FMN actuates as *antenna-pigment*, mediating molecules in solution. The formation of a surface FMN-monolayer for a fast electron transfer is consistent with the model of self-mediation¹⁷. The model of Armstrong *et al.*¹⁹ proposes that fast electron transfer occurs at isolated microscopic electroactive sites. These sites are presumably oxygen-containing and generated by surface polishing, which is the case of the systems under investigation. This results in surface functionalisation of oxide-Zn electrodes with FMN molecules, explaining the higher roughness factor (ρ) ($\Gamma^{\text{max}}/\Gamma^{\text{app}}$); the true microscopic surface area is larger than the macroscopically measured area (Table 2). The ρ values are quite low if compared to earlier work⁷; the mechanical polishing of electrodes during preparation (experimental section) reduced the difference between smooth and roughened surfaces of Zn electrodes.

Fig. 6. Diagram illustrating the applied potential effect [E_{ads} (\bullet) = -1.0 V and E_{ads} (\diamond) = -1.2 V , adsorption time = 60 s] vs concentration for FMN solutions/Zn-oxide electrodes under monochromatic light at 450 nm .

Fig. 6 reveals that systems with adsorption potentials

at -1.2 V are insensitive to the FMN solution concentration (J_p is constant), but varied linearly for adsorption potential -1.0 V. If dissolved FMN can only transfer electrons to the electrode via the adsorbed molecules, it means that the adsorbed FMN quantity remains constant at $E_{ads} = -1.2$ V. The oxide layer formed onto Zn electrodes at $E_{ads} = -1.0$ V, adsorbs FMN molecules until Γ^{max} value is reached (dependent on equilibrium concentration C_{eq}).

FMN and RF present distinct adsorption and photoelectrochemical behaviour, which can be related to its molecular structure. The phosphate group (FMN) appears to be more effective with monochromatic light in the processes of electron transfer to the solid electrode surface, due to higher adsorption properties on interfaces; higher extent of probability for the wave function overlap between metal substrate and adsorbate; electronic excitation ($\lambda_{max} = 450$ nm) promotes electron tunneling to the metal by resonant charge transfer^{5,18} (excitation above Fermi level). RF presents reduced adsorption properties, weaker electronic coupling between RF and the oxide-zinc electrode, no apparent surface mediation (actuators) of RF to solution molecules (Fig. 6) due to poor energy compatibility/mediation between solid and solution RF molecules, so that only adsorbed molecules (the electroactive sites generated by adsorption) are responsible for charge injection. The mechanisms of electron transfer between RF and solid electrodes are still nuclear. Additional information about energy-controlling steps, supplemented by optical and magnetic measurements would elucidate adsorptive and photochemical mechanisms for flavins.

Experimental

Flavin mononucleotide (FMN) disodium salt (Fluka) was recrystallised from acidic solution (2.0 M acetic acid)²⁰. Riboflavin was recrystallised from 2 M acetic acid and then extracted with $CHCl_3$ to remove lumichrome impurities²¹. The ZnO powder isolated from ethanol (5-day aged solution; particle diameter ≈ 5 nm) was prepared according to the method described earlier¹⁰. The specific surface area of ZnO reported in the literature¹⁵ is 10 m² g⁻¹ and was used to estimate the surface density of adsorbed FMN and RF. The zero point of charge (pcz), by using 0.1 M LiOH at preparation, was reached at pH 6.5 ¹⁰. Experiments employed 2.0 ml of KCl (0.1 M) and acetate-buffer at pH 4.00 and varied flavin (FMN and RF) concentrations. ZnO (2.0 mg) was added to these solutions and stirred for 20 min at 25° to reach the adsorption equilibrium. The solutions were centrifuged or passed through millipore filtering systems (Millipore AG, type GC, 0.45 μ m pore size). Reproducibility was achieved for both methods without expressive discrepancies ($\pm 5\%$).

FMN and RF present extinction coefficient⁹ at 448 nm

(λ_{max}), $\epsilon_{448} = 12300$ M⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The difference in the absorbance at 448 nm of the initial and filtered solutions was used to calculate the equilibrium concentrations, by using a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 2000 spectrophotometer.

Electrochemical measurements : The zinc electrodes were prepared by mechanical surface polishing with emery paper cleaned with distilled water, degreased with carbon tetrachloride, acetone and ethanol with surface area varying from 0.2 to 1.5 cm². The smooth Zn electrodes (polished) so prepared were immersed in electrolyte solutions [Li_2SO_4 0.1 M, HQ (hidroquine) 0.1 M, the redox couple; pH = 5.0 adjusted with H_2SO_4 1 M] of an conventional three-electrode electrochemical cell, employing a Pt-wire as auxiliary electrode, a SCE as reference and the zinc as working electrode. FMN and RF were dissolved in these solutions, with concentrations in the range 10^{-5} to 10^{-4} M. Prior to recording the cyclic voltammograms, N_2 gas was passed into the electrolyte solution for at least 30 min in order to remove oxygen. The light effect was characterised by illumination through the electrolyte (light incident upon the electrolyte-electrode interface) as described in the literature²²⁻²⁴. A 150 W Xe lamp was used as white light or in conjunction with a monochromator 450 nm, by considering that the absorption maximum for FMN and RF is located at 448 nm. The cathodic peak current density-II (J_p mA cm⁻²) was selected to monitor the blank experiments with the following variables : concentrations : FMN (zero, 0.028 and 0.1 mM), RF (zero, 0.55 mM); irradiation conditions : dark, white light and monochromatic light ($\lambda = 450$ nm); adsorption time : 15 and 60 s (the 60 s adsorption time showed to be more effective, so most experiments were conducted under these conditions); adsorption potential : $E_{ads} = -1.20$ V and $E_{ads} = -1.00$ V. The scan rate of 2 mV s⁻¹ at 100 mA/V, changes linearly with time from initial potential (E_i) 1.20 V to final potential (E_f) 0.90 V. The constancy of the peak potential (E_p) values in different systems (Table 2) evidenced electrode stability, with unchanged physicochemical properties during electrochemical measurements.

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was performed using a PAR 173 potentiostat with a PAR 376 logarithm current convensor and a function programmer PAR 175; the voltammograms were recorded with a Houston RE0089-PAR recorder as described before^{25,26}.

All experiments were made in duplicate at $(25 \pm 1)^\circ$.

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